

Instructional Program on Nurses' Knowledge and practice Towards Nursing Documentation in Pediatric Wards

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ABSTRACT

Background: Nursing documentation is a set of written information, transmitted in the form of a document with regard to patient's health and care status, It is a legal and professional action for people involved in health care affairs, including nurses.

Objectives: To determine Instructional Program on Nurses' Knowledge and practice Towards Nursing Documentation in Pediatric Wards at Mosul Hospitals.

Methods: Quasi-experimental design through using (Non probability) Purposive Sampling was conducted to determine Effectiveness of an Instructional Program on nurses' knowledge and practice Nursing documentation in Pediatric Wards at Mosul Hospitals from 13 October 2023 throughout 14 March 2024. A simple random sample with probability of 60 sample . Data is analyzed using the "Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software for Windows (Version 26)"

Results: This finding the showed that those aged 30-34 had the highest percentage (46.7%). In regards to sex, more than half of the study sample were female (60%) as compared with those who were male. Regarding educational level, the percentage was almost equal. Years of relevant experience resulted in a mean of 2.53.

Conclusion: This study concluded that before giving the program, nurses' knowledge and practice were very weak, and after giving the program, their knowledge and practice became good and continued until the second test.

KEYWORDS: Instructional Program, Nurses' Knowledge, practice, Nursing Documentation, Pediatric Wards.

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INTRODUCTION

Nursing documentation started to become more standardized in the early 20th century as hospitals and other healthcare facilities realized how important it was to provide high-quality patient care. The discipline of nursing documentation grew further with the creation of standardized nomenclature and classification schemes, which made record-keeping more thorough and uniform⁽¹⁾. Over the past few decades, there has been a significant shift in the nursing profession about the need for numerous independent skills for a thorough grasp of nursing care. The necessity of recording more than only the medical and nursing treatment provided⁽²⁾. In the 1980s and early 1990s, major health-related organizations and a number of western countries began to develop standards, laws, and rules stating that nursing care

must be implemented in nursing documentation⁽³⁾. Nursing documentation was completely transformed when electronic health records (EHRs) were introduced in the late 20th century. This was made possible by the ability of nurses to precisely and efficiently document patient care. EHRs also made it easier for healthcare professionals to collaborate and communicate with one another, which enhanced continuity of care and improved patient outcomes⁽⁴⁾. Nursing documentation is changing in the modern day due to changes in healthcare delivery methods and technological improvements. In order to make it simpler to access and update patient information in real-time, nurses are increasingly documenting patient care using mobile devices and digital platforms^(5,6).

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METHODS AND MATERIALS

Quasi-experimental design through using (Non probability) Purposive Sampling was conducted to determine Effectiveness of an Instructional Program on nurses' knowledge and practice Nursing documentation in Pediatric Wards at Mosul Hospitals from 13 October 2023 throughout 14 March 2024. The study was carried out in the Mosul city , centre of Nineveh Governorate, located in northern Iraq. Mosul is the second largest city in Iraq. The study was applied as a (Study and control group) in pediatric departments from five hospitals distributed on both sides of the Tigris River in Mosul city: Four from five hospitals are located on the left side of Mosul city (Al Salam teaching hospital, Ibn-Sena Teaching Hospital, Ibn Al Atheer pediatric teaching hospital and Al Khansa'a teaching hospital) all of them are educational. As for the other hospital (Mosul general hospital), they are located on the right side of the city, is a

general hospital, and all of them (5 hospitals) are affiliated to the Iraqi Ministry of Health / Nineveh Health Department. Purposive Sampling (Non-probability) of nurses for the two group with different position. The sample was collected for the Study group in pediatric departments of Mosul hospitals. They were (60) nurses who work in Pediatric Wards, who agreed to participate in the study. Purposive sampling was made by choosing (30) nurses from (5) hospitals as a (study group), each hospital (6) nurses. As well as by choosing (30) nurses from (5) hospitals as a control group, (6) nurses from each hospital. Each person needs about 30 to 40 minutes to complete the questionnaire. Data is analyzed using the "Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software for Windows (Version 26)" ⁽⁷⁻¹⁰⁾. This study (Study code 433/6521) received approval from the Ministry of Health's recently formed Ethics Committee. Individual informed consent was not needed, the review panel determined.

RESULTS

Table (1) :Distribution of the two samples (study and control) in terms of socio-demographic for research sample (60 Nurses)

Demographic data	variable	sample	Freq.	%
Age	20-24	Study	2	6.7
		Control	2	6.7
	25-29	Study	4	13.3
		Control	5	16.7
	30-34	Study	14	46.7
		Control	7	23.3
	35-39	Study	4	13.3
		Control	7	23.3
40-44	Study	6	20	
	Control	9	30	
sex	Male	Study	12	40
		Control	12	40
	Female	Study	18	60
		Control	18	60
Educational level	School Nursing	Study	13	43.3
		Control	11	36.7
	Institute Nursing	Study	7	23.3
		Control	11	36.7
	College of Nursing	Study	10	33.3
		Control	8	26.7
Experience	Mean	Study	2.53	
		Control	3.53	
Have you participated in training courses	Yes	Study	3	10
		Control	4	13.3
	No	Study	27	90
		Control	26	86.7
Number of courses	0	Study	27	90
		Control	26	86.7
	1	Study	3	10
		Control	4	13.3

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The results in the table (1) show that the sample size was 60, of which 30 were the study samples and the other 30 were the control samples. The demographic data of participants showed that those aged 30-34 had the highest percentage (46.7%). In regards to sex, more than half of the study sample were female (60%) as compared with those who were male.

Regarding educational level, the percentage was almost equal. Years of relevant experience resulted in a mean of 2.53. In terms of training courses, most participants did not participate in training (90%) compared to those who participated in one course.

Table (2) : Assessing study sample of nurses' knowledge and practice (pre-test), (post-test 1), and (post-test 2).

Type of knowledge	Total score average		Evaluation
KNOWLEDGE ABOUT NURSING DOCUMENTATION	Pre	2.80	poor
	Post1	8.70	Good
	Post2	7.90	Good
KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THE PATIENT'S ADMISSION FORM	Pre	1.63	Poor
	Post1	7.33	Good
	Post2	7.17	Good
KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THE VITAL SIGNS FORM	Pre	1.87	Poor
	Post1	5.63	Accepted
	Post2	5.47	Accepted
KNOWLEDGE ABOUT THE NURSING CARE PLAN FORM	Pre	3.03	Poor
	Post1	8.80	Good
	Post2	8.57	Good
Practice	Pre	2.00	Poor
	Post1	9.80	Good
	Post2	9.00	Good

The results are shown in Table 2. The nurses' knowledge and practice were poor in the (pre-test), compared to their knowledge and practice in (post-test 1) and (post-test 2).

DISCUSSION

Nursing Documentation helps document all the care and services patients receive. Important information such as assessment of the patient's condition, measures taken, medications given and procedures performed are recorded. This helps provide a detailed and up-to-date record of the patient's condition, facilitates monitoring of changes in their condition and improves the quality of care⁽¹¹⁾. Documentation reflected this religious influence, with care records intertwined with spiritual observations and moral reflections on the patient's condition. Care records were scarce and often consisted of informal, handwritten notes. The focus was primarily on practical information like medications administered, treatments performed, and basic observations

like pulse or breathing. Detailed clinical data, such as vital signs or progress notes, were rarely recorded⁽¹²⁾. The results in the table (1) show that the sample size was 60, of which 30 were the study samples and the other 30 were the control samples. The demographic data of participants showed that those aged 30-34 had the highest percentage (46.7%). In regards to sex, more than half of the study sample were female (60%) as compared with those who were male. Regarding educational level, the percentage was almost equal. Years of relevant experience resulted in a mean of 2.53. In terms of training courses, most participants did not participate in training (90%) compared to those who participated in one course. The results are shown in Table 2. The nurses' knowledge and practice were poor in the (pre-

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test), compared to their knowledge and practice in (post-test 1) and (post-test 2). From the second table, during the first test of the two patients regarding nursing documentation, it was found that their knowledge and practice regarding nursing documentation was weak. After giving an intensive program for a week and testing the sample a second time, their knowledge and practice became good. The reason is due to the effectiveness of the program. Then the sample was examined after two months to determine the duration of maintenance. They also had good knowledge and practice

CONCLUSION

This study concluded that before giving the program, nurses' knowledge and practice were very weak, and after giving the program, their knowledge and practice became good and continued until the second test.

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